

Self-Aligned Photonic Defect Microcavity Lasers with Site-Controlled Quantum Dots

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Self-assembled semiconductor quantum dots face challenges in terms of scalable device integration because of their random growth positions, originating from the Stranski–Krastanov growth mode. Even with existing site-controlled growth techniques, for example, nanohole or buried stressor concepts, a further lithography and etching step with high spatial alignment requirements is necessary to accurately integrate quantum dots into the nanophotonic devices. Here, the fabrication and characterization of strain-induced site-controlled microcavities are reported, where site-controlled quantum dots are positioned at the antinode of the optical mode field in a self-aligned manner without the need of any further nano-processing. It is shown that the cavity properties such as Q-factor, mode volume, and mode splitting can be tailored by the geometry of the integrated buried stressor, with an opening $<4\ \mu\text{m}$. The experimental results are complemented with theory calculations based on continuum elasticity. Lasing signatures, including super-linear input-output response and linewidth narrowing, are observed for a $3.6\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ self-aligned cavity with a Q-factor of 18 000. Furthermore, the quasi-planar site-controlled cavities exhibit no detrimental thermal effects. This approach integrates seamlessly with the industrial-matured manufacturing process and the buried-stressor technique, paving the way for exceptional scalability and straightforward manufacturing of high- β microlasers and bright quantum light sources.

1. Introduction

Semiconductor quantum dots (QDs), acting as artificial atoms, have demonstrated superiority in a variety of emerging quantum technologies due to their exceptional optical properties. These include adjustable emission wavelength covering from the visible range to telecommunication bands,^[1] near-unity quantum efficiency,^[2] on-demand single-photon, and entangled photon pair emission.^[3–5] Furthermore, the choice of the zero-dimensional (0D) QDs over two-dimensional (2D) quantum wells (QWs) can lead to improved laser properties such as low threshold power, high temperature stability,^[6,7] and ultimately high- β factors facilitating strong light-matter interaction with cavity quantum electrodynamics (cQED) effects.^[8–11] Additionally, it is crucial for the development of quantum light sources for applications in photonic quantum information technologies.^[12]

Nevertheless, standard QDs face significant challenges in epitaxially controlling their spectral inhomogeneous broadening and spatial nucleation position due to the self-assembled nature of Stranski-Krastanov (SK) growth. These issues hinder the scalable integration of QDs into nanophotonic structures, which aim to enhance the light extraction, emission rate, and light-matter coupling for optimum device performance. Spectral matching of single QDs and the optical modes of microresonators has been successfully addressed with multiple techniques including piezoelectric strain tuning,^[13–15] quantum confined Stark effect tuning,^[16,17] and temperature tuning.^[18] The spatial matching, on the other hand, is addressed through post-growth deterministic nano-fabrication techniques like in-situ or marker-based optical and electron beam lithography (EBL),^[19–21] pre-growth nanoholes patterning,^[22] and the buried-stressor growth method.^[23,24]

The buried-stressor growth technique for site-controlled quantum dots (SCQDs) is particularly intriguing due to its ability to ensure high optical quality of the QDs thanks to the high-quality growth surface,^[25,26] control of their position and local density,^[27,28] and seamless integration within the industry-scale vertical cavity surface emitting lasers (VCSELs) process flow.^[29]

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Figure 1. Illustration of the fabrication process of SCMs. a) 1st-step epitaxial growth of oxidation templates. b) Square mesa etching and partial lateral wet-oxidation to form a size- and site-controlled oxide aperture. c) 2nd-step overgrowth with InGaAs QDs and top DBRs. The reddish ellipse in (c) depicts the mode confined by the photonic defect cavity. d) Optical microscope image of a site-controlled microcavity self-aligned to the site-controlled QDs.

Photonic devices, such as single-photon sources (SPS)^[25–27,30] and micropillar lasers^[28] based on SCQDs have been demonstrated. Nevertheless, most site-controlled growth techniques including the buried stressor method still require a post-position-alignment step for the integration of SCQDs into photonic microcavities, which involves either marker-based or in situ lithography.^[31–36] The situation can become even more complex when the pre-patterned markers are overgrown and covered by thick layers such as distributed Bragg reflectors (DBRs), which could obstruct the visual identification of the markers.^[27,28]

QDs are often integrated into micro- and nano-cavities with small mode volume to harness the cavity enhancement originating from, for instance, the Purcell-effect in the weak coupling regime of cQED. Despite the achieved performance, for instance, photon extraction efficiency exceeding 65% in micropillar^[37,38] and 85% in circular Bragg grating (CBG) resonator configurations,^[5] accompanying issues related to thermal management^[39,40] and detrimental surface defect states^[41] arise. Microcavities based on buried photonic defects, where no deep etching is required, can overcome these issues, and have recently caught significant interest from the nanophotonics community.^[42–45] In such quasi-planar microcavities, usually the upper DBRs are shaped into micro- or nano-lenses to laterally confine light.

In this study, we present an innovative type of a quasi-planar site-controlled microcavity (SCM) created through the buried-stressor method. This SCM forms in a self-assembled manner during epitaxial growth and is spatially self-aligned to the SCQDs, eliminating the need for any post-growth lithography. We take advantage of the fact that the strain induced by the buried stressor can modulate the growth rate and reshape the morphology of the sequential layers including the upper DBR, and can therefore form a photonic defect providing strong lateral mode

confinement. Interestingly, as we show below, microcavity properties such as Q-factor and mode volume can be tailored by the geometry of SCM, which is controlled by the size of the oxide aperture.

In the following, we first describe the fabrication and formation of SCMs and SCQDs by means of the buried-stressor method, together with a theoretical investigation on the strain and optical aspects of SCMs. Afterward, we present the experimental characterization of SCMs with pump power dependent micro-photoluminescence measurements on SCMs with different full width at half maximum (FWHM). Finally, we demonstrate lasing action of SCM, proving the high potential of our approach for nanophotonic applications.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Fabrication of SCMs

A crucially appealing aspect of the SCM concept is the fact that the related device fabrication is not only synchronized but also spatially self-aligned with the buried-stressor growth of SCQDs. The fabrication process can be divided into three major steps as illustrated in **Figure 1**. It starts with a) the 1st-step metal-organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) growth of oxidation templates with bottom DBR, followed by b) mesa etching and lateral wet-oxidation of the AlAs layer to create the oxide aperture, and c) the 2nd-step overgrowth by InGaAs QDs and the top DBR.

In our device structure discussed here, the bottom (top) DBR consists of 31 (27) alternating $\text{Al}_{0.9}\text{Ga}_{0.1}\text{As}/\text{GaAs}$ layer pairs with quarter-wavelength thickness of 77.8/66.7 nm. The oxidation aperture in **Figure 1** consists of a 30-nm-thick AlAs oxidation layer embedded in two 50 nm thick $\text{Al}_{0.9}\text{Ga}_{0.1}\text{As}$ layers for mechanical stabilization. In the growth of the oxidation templates,

80 nm of GaAs is deposited on the surface to encapsulate the AlAs layer to prevent surface oxidation, as illustrated in Figure 1a. Square mesas with a side length of $\approx 20 \mu\text{m}$ are then patterned via UV-lithography using a Hg lamp before being exposed to water vapor at 420°C , laterally oxidizing the AlAs layer as illustrated in Figure 1b. The lateral oxidation process is interrupted before fully oxidizing the AlAs layer, leaving an opening that we denote as oxide aperture. Systematic control of the oxide aperture is enabled by varying the side length of the square mesas in 67-nm steps in conjunction with in-situ optical microscope monitoring of the oxidation process. In the consecutive 2nd-step overgrowth, the InGaAs QDs are preferentially grown above the tensile-strained aperture because of the surface strain modulated by the oxide aperture.^[23,24] Interestingly, in our SCM concept we utilize the induced strain not only for spatially controlling the QD nucleation site but also the thickness of all the subsequent layers, including the top DBR. During the deposition process of the upper DBR, the growth rate and thickness is modulated in a spatially dependent manner, causing the mirror layers of the top DBR above the oxide aperture to curve into a lens shape as illustrated in Figure 1c along with a microscope image in Figure 1d. Noteworthy, this industry-compatible process without any further post-growth lithography is sufficient to fabricate the SCM devices with three-dimensional (3D) mode confinement.

2.2. Morphology of SCM and Theoretical Investigations

To verify the strain-modulated growth of the upper DBR, we performed atomic force microscopy (AFM) to scan the surface morphology of SCMs with various oxide aperture sizes as presented in Figure 2a–c. Micro- and nano-lenses, isolated and surrounded by trenches, can be observed in the center of the mesas, that is, directly above the oxide aperture. Please note that an ellipticity in the shape of SCM is observed, which can lift the degeneracy of the fundamental cavity mode and lead to a mode energy splitting as observed in bimodal micropillar lasers with asymmetric cross-section.^[46,47]

To better understand the origin of the SCM formation verified by the surface morphology obtained from the AFM measurements, we performed strain tensor calculations on the conceived structure depicted in Figure 1c using continuum elasticity theory.^[48–50] Since the AFM measurements provide information about relative height in different parts of the surface, we focused on the calculations on vertical strain, that is, ϵ_{zz} strain component, where z is oriented along the [001] crystal direction. The parameter ϵ_{zz} then reveals the expected out-of-plane expansion or contraction of the crystal lattice toward the surface, which is then reflected by the surface morphology observed with AFM. The computed surface strain ϵ_{zz} in panels (d)–(f) highly resembles the AFM profiles in (a)–(c), with an increase of the ϵ_{zz} in the center, directly above the aperture, surrounded by diminishing ϵ_{zz} . Moreover, in order to manifest the realism of our theory description and the agreement of that with experiment, we have integrated the z -component of the lattice displacement vector u_z , which is obtained alongside our continuum elasticity computations.^[51] The integration of that was performed from the buried aperture up to the heterostructure surface, and the results are shown in Figure 2g–i. Moreover, we note that usually

the surface topography is computed using, for example, finite element method (FEM),^[52] hence, we provide here an alternative approach to compute that using continuum elasticity, which is both conceptually and numerically easier to employ. Further details on our numerical calculations are provided in the Experimental Section.

With two orthogonal linescans of each AFM profile, we further analyzed the peak-to-valley height of the lenses as a function of their FWHM, fitted by a Gaussian lineshape, as exemplified in Figure 3a–c, corresponding to the SCMs presented in Figure 2a–c with FWHM of a) $1.1 \mu\text{m}$, b) $2.4 \mu\text{m}$, and c) $3.6 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. Due to the lack of circular symmetry of the SCMs (see AFM images in Figure 2), their height and FWHM are estimated by averaging two orthogonal line profiles per AFM image. Interestingly, the extracted height increases linearly with the FWHM as shown in Figure 3d, which can potentially affect the strength of lateral confinement. Meanwhile, the AFM surface characterization of the SCQDs layer underneath the top DBRs has revealed an additional abrupt small bump $\approx 8 \text{ nm}$ existing above the oxide aperture, which can be attributed to Indium migration during epitaxial growth^[53] (please see the Supporting Information). The computed surface morphology from the vertical integral of displacement u_z using the continuum elasticity theory [see Figure 2g–i] exhibits a similar behavior in the SCM FWHM-height relationship as shown in Figure 3e, where the values are extracted in the same manner as the AFM profiles in Figure 3a–c. The excellent correspondence between the AFM profiles and the calculated demonstrates that the whole crystal lattice of the upper layers is distorted due to the buried stressor. Overall, the lens-shape morphology indicates that in our self-aligned fabrication concept, not only the growth of the SCQDs, but also the cavity geometry can be tailored and controlled by the size and shape of the oxide aperture.

Figure 4a presents a cross-section scanning-electron microscopy (SEM) image of a structure with a notably large oxide aperture. A kink, traced by an arrow, along the upper layers of the SEM image implies how the strain exerted by the AlAs/Al₂O₃ aperture propagates toward the surface. Due to the oxidation inhomogeneity and the lack of direct measurement of the absolute oxide aperture size after overgrowth, we plot the SCM FWHM measured from another more homogenous array as a function of the nominal variation of the square mesa size as shown in Figure 4b. The array, however, has a smaller range of oxide aperture size variation, purely limited by the design of our UV-lithography mask. Although there are still a few outliers resulting from oxidation inhomogeneity, the positive correlation between the mesa size and the SCM FWHM evidences that the SCM FWHM can be controlled by the oxide aperture size, that is, the mesa size. A linear solid line with a slope of 1 is also plotted as a guide to the eye.

To gain more insights, we performed theory calculations of ϵ_{zz} strain, as presented in Figure 4c. An excerpt of the simulated structure in (c) corresponds in all dimensions to that for experimental SEM in (a). The calculation clearly indicates that the magnitude of ϵ_{zz} in GaAs DBR layers increases from more (white) toward less (dark gray) compressive strain as one moves from the AlAs/Al₂O₃ oxide aperture toward the sample surface. Moreover, the magnitude of ϵ_{zz} strain increases in “cone” similarly as in our SEM image. However, the “kink” on the sample surface

Figure 2. AFM images of SCMs with FWHM of a) 1.1 μm , b) 2.4 μm , and c) 3.6 μm . Note that the FWHM here is determined by fitting a Gaussian around the central bump to represent the size of the SCMs, which is explained later in Figure 3. We also show the computed surface distributions of the z component of the strain tensor ϵ_{zz} for aperture sizes of d) 0.2 μm , e) 1 μm , and f) 2 μm and computed integral of vertical component of displacement vector u_z (see text) again for aperture sizes of g) 0.2 μm , h) 1 μm , and i) 2 μm . The range of magnitudes of ϵ_{zz} strain in (d)–(f) is between -0.1% (violet) to -0.02% (green). We would like to remark the relative increase of ϵ_{zz} above aperture (light blue) in (d)–(f) and that for integral of u_z (dark red) in (g)–(i) with respect to the surrounding surface {violet in (d)–(f) and blue in (g)–(i)} and agreement of the theory with the AFM images in (a)–(c).

layer is related to a more gradual change of ϵ_{zz} as indicated by the inset arrow. Furthermore, in Figure 4d, we show the aperture diameter as a function of integral u_z FWHM obtained from our calculations. Considering a constant oxidation rate, the mesa size increment should equal the oxide aperture diameter increment. As a result, the experimental and theoretical observations in (b) and (d) are in very good quantitative agreement, where the SCM FWHM increases as a function of the aperture diameter with a slope of 1 for both cases.

To investigate the optical properties of SCMs, optical simulations are carried out by means of a commercial software package, JCMsuite, based on the finite element method (FEM).^[54] The modeling of the structure is described in the Experimen-

tal Section. Figure 4f shows the optical field of the fundamental cavity mode confined by an SCM with an exemplary aperture diameter of 2.5 μm . The mode field extends out of the oxide aperture, resulting in a strong spatial overlap between the SCQDs and the mode field antinode, which maximizes the light confinement and the Purcell factors of the integrated QD emitters. Furthermore, the self-aligned overlap of SCQDs and modes is advantageous for improving the interaction between light and matter and for minimizing the absorption losses attributed to off-center QDs.^[28] The simulation yields a theoretical cavity Q-factor of 144 000 and mode volume of 44.1 $(\lambda/n)^3$, which would result in a Purcell factor of 248 in the ideal case of perfect spatial and spectral alignment. We would, however, like to remark that the mode

Figure 3. Exemplary AFM linescan profiles along with Gaussian fits of the SCM presented in Figure 2a–c with FWHM of a) 1.1 μm, b) 2.4 μm, and c) 3.6 μm, respectively. d) The peak-to-valley height of SCM as a function of the FWHM. The presented SCM FWHM and height are averaged from two orthogonal line profiles. e) The same as in (d) but derived from the integral of u_z lattice displacement computed by the continuum elasticity theory.

parameters of such buried photonic cavities are highly sensitive to the shape and morphology of the defect structure. For instance, a Gaussian-shape defect cavity would have a significantly higher Q-factor than a simple mesa defect cavity.^[43] Therefore, without using nano-resolution imaging techniques such as the transmission electron microscopy (TEM) to accurately retrieve the layer structures for modeling, the presented simulation is expected to deviate from the experiments considerably.

2.3. Optical Characterization of SCMs

We experimentally characterized the optical properties of SCMs using a micro-photoluminescence (μ PL) setup, where the sample is mounted in a He-flow cryostat at 20 K and optically pumped by a continuous wave (CW) laser at 785 nm followed by a spectrometer with a spectral resolution of 55 μ eV. **Figure 5** shows pump-power and polarization dependent measurements of an SCM with a FWHM of 2.7 μ m. Interestingly, two ensembles of optical modes can be observed in the μ PL spectra, as shown in Figure 5a–c. We attribute the presence of these two groups of modes to lateral light confinement arising from the strain-induced aperture cavity and the mesa cavity, respectively. Here, tight lateral light confinement in the strain-induced aperture cavity is caused by the curved layers of the top DBR directly above the oxide aperture, which we denote as SCM throughout the article. The overgrown etched square mesa with a length of 20 μ m also leads

to lateral mode confinement, similar to other previous etch-then-deposit approaches.^[44,45] However, the associated mode volume is significantly larger, and as a result, compared to the aperture cavity the mesa cavity leads to smaller mode spacing as a sign of larger mode volume. Observed typical mode spacings of the aperture cavity and the mesa cavity are 1–10 meV and 0.2 meV, respectively. Noteworthy, the aperture cavity modes are spatially centered and self-aligned to the SCQDs. On the other hand, because of deviations of the structural geometry, the mesa cavity modes are typically located slightly off-center of the oxide aperture by >2 μ m and are therefore spatially mismatched to the SCQDs.

We would like to note that the strain-induced aperture cavity modes have a lower energy than the mesa cavity modes. That, on the first sight surprising feature, can be attributed to the fact that the aperture cavity modes are confined in vertical direction by a larger thickness of the central cavity region above the oxide aperture. Here, the larger thickness is confirmed by our AFM measurements (see Figure 2 and the **Supporting Information**). Since the vertical mode confinement is stronger than the lateral one, small changes in the cavity thickness have a strong influence on the mode energy. The mentioned mode confinement effects are further verified by 1-D numerical simulations with the transfer matrix method (TMM), investigating the mode energy on and off the oxidized area. The simulations show that a simple GaAs cavity just 8 nm thicker with a non-oxidized AlAs layer can redshift the mode energy by ≈ 10 meV, fitting our experimental observation. Please see the **Supporting Information** for more details on the TMM simulation. Furthermore, with polarization dependent

Figure 4. a) Cross-section SEM image of an SCM showing the propagation of the profile kink from the oxide aperture edge. b) The SCM FWHM as a function of the nominal mesa size increment. The red linear line is a plot with a slope of 1 as a guide to the eye. c) Cutout from the strain calculation corresponding to the SEM measurement (a). The gray DBR layers in (c) correspond to GaAs while the black ones to $\text{Al}_{0.9}\text{Ga}_{0.1}\text{As}$. The kink on the surface seen in (a) occurs as a gradual lateral change of ϵ_{zz} magnitude on the top sample surface layer and is indicated by an inset arrow in (c). d) The computed SCM FWHM and the associated aperture diameter derived from the calculated integral of the lattice displacement u_z . The fitted line has a slope of 1. e) Eigenmode optical simulation of a modeled SCM with an aperture diameter of 2.5 μm. In the heatmap, higher mode field intensity is displayed in red and lower mode field intensity is displayed in blue. The opening of the oxide aperture is denoted as the SCQDs growth area, self-aligned to the antinode of the SCM mode field.

measurements we find that the non-circular shape of the aperture cavity also lifts the degeneracy of the fundamental mode, leading to two orthogonally polarized modes with a spectral splitting of 20 μeV as shown in Figure 5d. Such a phenomenon has also been observed in bimodal micropillar lasers with asymmetric cross-section.^[46,47] These two mode components are marked as fundamental mode 1 and mode 2 in Figure 5e. Note that the mesa cavity modes also exhibit a high degree of linear polarization (please see the Supporting Information). Without intentionally increasing the number of SCQDs, for instance, by stacking multiple layers of high density SCQDs,^[53] most of the oxide apertures contain a low number of SCQDs. In fact, less than 20 SCQDs are formed for mesas with oxide aperture diameter in the range of 700 to 1400 nm in our sample.^[28] As a result, most of the structures do not exhibit the characteristic S-curve in the I/O or power dependent linewidth narrowing as lasing signatures due to the inadequate modal gain to surpass the laser threshold. These excitation power dependent properties are exemplified in Figure 5e. Note that even though a slight nonlinearity can be observed in the I/O curves in Figure 5e, the phenomenon can potentially be attributed to the complex gain competition between the two modes,

which is accompanied by the linewidth jittering as also observed in micropillar lasers.^[40]

To systematically investigate the strain-modulated growth of the subsequent upper layers, we performed AFM studies to scan the surface morphology of the fabricated SCMs with various oxide aperture sizes, as presented in Figure 2a–c. As already observed in the microscope image shown in Figure 1e, microlenses, isolated and surrounded by trenches, are located at the center of the mesas and vertically aligned to the AIAs opening of the oxide aperture. As a height difference up to 80 nm is observed in the AFM profiles, the effect can not simply be attributed to the volume shrinkage of the 30-nm-thick AIAs layer, but to the strain-modulated growth induced by the oxide aperture. Figure 6a shows the cavity Q-factor as a function of SCM FWHM evaluated at low pump power. The Q-factor increases from ≈8000 to 18 000 when the FWHM increases from 2.0 to 3.6 μm. Below 2 μm no clear trend in Q-factor is observed, potentially due to the complexity of the overall SCM shape accompanying the FWHM variation as shown in Figure 2. The mode energy, on the other hand, strongly blueshifts with decreasing SCM FWHM as shown in Figure 6b. That effect can be attributed to two factors: first,

Figure 5. Pump power and polarization dependent μ PL measurements of an SCM with a FWHM of 2.7 μm . a–c) μ PL spectra of fundamental mode 1 collected at the center of the mesa at pump powers of 5.6 mW, 1.9 mW, and 0.2 mW, respectively. The arrows indicate the aperture cavity modes. d) The aperture mode energy fitted as a function of the polarization angle. The inset shows the spectra of the two orthogonal polarized fundamental modes. e) Pump power dependent output intensity and linewidth of the aperture cavity mode. The solid squares belong to the output power and the open circles belong to the linewidth. The arrows indicate the powers corresponding to (a)–(c).

the mode radius decreases with decreasing SCM FWHM^[55]; and second, the optical cavity thickness is also reduced as presented in Figure 2. Figure 6c shows the 1st-2nd mode and fundamental mode splitting as a function of SCM FWHM. The increase of 1st-2nd mode splitting with decreasing SCM FWHM is a further experimental indication that the mode is laterally confined and controlled by the SCM FWHM, and therefore by the size of the oxide aperture, with reference to the case of cylindrical Fabry-Pérot microcavities.^[55] Note that below 2 μm FWHM, along with the large amount of blueshift and a 1st-2nd mode splitting exceeding 9 meV, the higher order modes of the SCMs are spectrally indistinguishable from the mesa cavity mode ensemble. Moreover, the splitting between the two orthogonally polarized fundamental modes is also affected by the SCM's FWHM. As the SCM becomes smaller, the non-circular shape leads to a significant splitting of up to 163 μeV . The amount of splitting reduces with increasing SCM size, indicating the reduction of SCM ellipticity.

The developed high-quality SCMs have high potential to act as QD microlasers with nanoengineered gain medium. To study the lasing action of our SCM, we selected a structure with 3.6 μm FWHM where we expected many SCQDs. We estimate the number of SCQDs to surpass 50, extrapolated from the previous study,^[28] interacting with the optical field of the cavity to provide sufficient optical gain to overcome the losses. The excitation-power-dependent spectra are presented in Figure 7a, where single mode lasing with the fundamental mode is observed. The SCM shows lasing signatures, including a characteristic S-shaped IO-curve in double-logarithmic scale and linewidth

narrowing near threshold reaching the resolution limit of 55 μeV of our spectrometer as depicted in Figure 7b. Similar to in the case of bimodal micropillar lasers, gain competition is also presented between the two orthogonal components of the fundamental modes, where mode 1 is the superior component. By means of a simple laser rate equation assuming a simple two-level system,^[56] we fitted the IO-curve of the superior lasing mode to extract a lasing threshold P_{th} of (6.7 ± 0.3) mW, defined as the threshold where the mean photon number reaches unity, and a spontaneous emission factor β of $(4.2 \pm 0.1) \times 10^{-4}$.

Another interesting feature of the SCM lasing performance is the excitation power dependence of the mode energy. Fitting the experimental emission spectra yields a pump power dependent blueshift of ≈ 260 μeV in the range from 0.5 to 30 mW, as shown in Figure 7c. This spectral shift can be attributed to the carrier-induced refractive index change, known as plasma effects.^[57,58] We emphasize that the DBRs in the structure consist of $\text{Al}_{0.9}\text{Ga}_{0.1}\text{As}$ and GaAs, which can optically absorb the pump laser at 785 nm, leading to low pump power conversion efficiency.^[40] In the case of deeply etched structures, such as micropillar lasers, this usually leads to heating of the devices, which induces undesired thermal effects such as a redshift of the mode energy.^[39,40] Noteworthy, such heating effects are not observed in our quasi-planar SCM, where the heat can be effectively dissipated with the non-isolated surroundings.

Intriguingly, all the presented cavity Q-factors of SCMs are comparable or even higher than for the case of etched micropillars with a diameter of 5.2 μm and slightly larger mode volume

Figure 6. Cavity a) Q-factor, b) mode energy, and c) mode splitting as a function of the FWHM. Note that the SCM with a FWHM of $3.6 \mu\text{m}$ locates at another array than the others on the wafer, where the epitaxial inhomogeneity of the layer thickness dominates over the local effects and therefore shifts its mode energy out of the expected trend.

on the same wafer, where the achieved cavity Q-factor is lower than 10 000.^[28] The lasing threshold (6.7 ± 0.3) mW of the SCM microlaser is similar to the values determined for $5.2\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ -diameter micropillar lasers, where the achieved lasing threshold ranges from 5 to 9 mW.^[28] Furthermore, the SCMs exhibit consistent characteristics with the other photonic defect cavity microresonators fabricated by the etch-and-deposit approach, whereas the cavity Q-factor and mode volume strongly reduces with decreasing defect diameters.^[43,45] Additionally, as reported by K. Gaur et al., one advantage of the photonic defect cavity microresonators is the small mode volume compared to micropillars and the fact that the QDs is far away from surface defect states at the etched semiconductor surface, which can deteriorate the QDs' optical properties.^[41,45] This ensures the high quality of our

SCMs and their potential for high-performance quantum light sources and micro-lasers applications.

We would like to note that not only the SCM mode energy but also the SCQDs emission energy are strongly influenced by the oxide aperture.^[53] In addition, with the inhomogeneous broadening of the SCQDs,^[26] spectral matching between the emitters and SCMs is not guaranteed without careful engineering. In this scenario, a small ensemble of QDs is adopted in this work to provide a broadband gain spectrum to study the SCMs. In another extreme, up to date, despite that single SCQDs with single photon emission have been realized,^[26] an efficient emission energy tuning knob of the SCQDs such as spectral tuning via the quantum confined Stark effect in electrically contacted structures is still under development, which will enable the controlled demonstration of single-QD emission effects in SCM-based quantum light sources and can pave the way to single-QD lasing effects as reported previously for photonic crystal nanocavities and micropillars.^[59,60]

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, we showed that by means of the buried-stressor growth method, not only SCQDs are preferably nucleating above the oxide aperture, but also SCMs are formed self-aligned to the SCQDs resulting from the strain-induced growth-rate and thickness modulation in the upper DBR. The latter leads to a tight 3D mode confinement with high cavity Q-factor and small mode volume without further post-growth lithography. Our experimental characterization reveals that the optical properties of SCMs such as Q-factor, mode energy, and mode volume are strongly influenced by the size of the oxide aperture. With the continuum elasticity theory, we theoretically investigate the morphology of the microcavities. Based on that, we further develop a method to compute the surface topography, which compares very well with results of our AFM measurements. Lasing, including a characteristic S-shaped I/O-curve in double-logarithmic scale and linewidth narrowing, was achieved for an SCM with a Q-factor of 18 000 and a rather large FWHM of $3.6 \mu\text{m}$, which has enough modal gain provided by SCQDs to overcome the optical losses. Additionally, no thermal-induced redshift of the mode energy is observed for the whole pump power range, highlighting the effectiveness of thermal dissipation in such quasi-planar structures.

Thanks to the fact that the formation of SCMs is induced by the buried stressor, no nanoscale lithography technique such as EBL is required in the fabrication process. In fact, UV-lithography as a highly scalable and cost-effective lithography technique is sufficient to create these microcavities with 3D mode confinement. The SCM concept is well aligned with the established manufacturing processes of VCSELs and SCQDs, enabling an immediately applicable approach for the production of scalable and high-quality nanophotonic devices utilizing QDs.

4. Experimental Section

Structural Modeling of SCMs for Optical Simulation: The difficulties of theoretically investigating the SCMs' optical performances lie in the precise structural modeling of the SCM topology. It has been shown that for such photonic defect cavities, the cavity Q-factor and the mode volume are

Figure 7. Pump power dependent measurement of a SCM with 3.6 μm FWHM. a) The pump power dependent spectra with normalized intensity. b) IO-curve and linewidth of both components of the fundamental modes. The solid markers represent the output powers, whereas the empty markers denote the linewidths. c) The pump power dependent mode energy.

highly sensitive to the shape and size of the defects buried underneath the top DBRs.^[43] In this work, the structures are modeled in the following way to match the available AFM and SEM profile: a) Rotational symmetry was assumed in the simulation in order to have as simple a model as possible, but of course never simpler. b) A small Gaussian bump with a height of 8 nm and a standard deviation of oxide aperture radius was introduced in the GaAs cavity layer before the top DBR as evidenced by the AFM profile on the SCQDs layer. Please see the Supporting Information for the AFM profile on the SCQDs layer. c) The thickness of each top DBR was modified according to an inverse Gaussian function: $t(r) = T \times (1 - A \times G(r, r_0))$, where $t(r)$ is the modulated thickness as a function of the radial position, T is the nominal thickness of each layer, $A = 0.015$ modifies the strength to match the peak-to-valley height from the surface AFM profile, and G is a normalized Gaussian function centered at r_0 with a standard deviation of $r_0/4$. For each layer, r_0 is let to propagate at 65° angle from the edge of the oxide aperture according to the SEM image.

Numerical Modeling of Elastic Strain: In this work, a continuum elasticity approach was used for modeling of the elastic strain in the structure using software Nextnano++.^[48] The method started with the definition of the simulated structure, which was in the case taken to be exactly the same as in Figure 1c including all dimensions therein. Each material in the structure was thereafter described by the corresponding elastic parameters from Nextnano++ software database. In case of alloys, a linear interpolation between parameters for constituent materials was employed. The elastic strain energy in the whole simulated structure was thereafter minimized on the finite difference grid. Furthermore, the elastic displacement vector is defined as^[51]:

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}) = \mathbf{r}'(\mathbf{r}) - \mathbf{r} \quad (1)$$

which is connected to distortion tensor by^[52]:

$$e_{ij} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial r_j}; \quad i, j \in \{x, y, z\} \quad (2)$$

The elastic tensor is then the symmetric part:

$$\epsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} (e_{ij} + e_{ji}) \quad (3)$$

It is noted that the finite difference method was used in favor of potentially more precise atomistic approaches^[49,61] because of the considerably large dimensions of the simulated structure, being on the order of several μm in each spatial extension.^[52]

Optical Measurements: The structures were investigated with a standard μPL setup. The sample was mounted in a He-flow cryostat operating at 20 K, optically excited by a CW laser at 785 nm with a microscope objective with 0.4 numerical aperture to focus the laser beam into a small spot $\approx 4 \mu\text{m}^2$ and simultaneously collected the sample emission. In the detection path, a rotatable lambda-half wave plate followed by a fixed linear polarizer were installed before the spectrometer to resolve the polarization dependency.

Laser Rate Equations Model Based on a Two-Level System: To qualitatively characterize the lasing threshold P_{th} and the β -factor of the SCM laser, a simple laser rate equation model based on a two-level system was applied.^[56] By solving the laser rate equations, the optical pump power P_{pump} can be expressed as a function of the output power P_{out} :

$$P_{pump}(A, B, \beta, \xi) = A \frac{\gamma}{\beta} \left[\frac{BP_{out}}{1 + BP_{out}} (1 + \xi) (1 + \beta BP_{out}) - \beta \xi BP_{out} \right] \quad (4)$$

where A is the pump scaling parameter, B is the output scaling parameter linking the intracavity photon number to the measured output power, $\xi = n_0 \beta / \gamma \tau_{sp}$ is a dimensionless factor with n_0 the exciton number at transparency threshold, τ_{sp} the spontaneous emission rate, γ the cavity decay rate, and β the spontaneous emission factor. On the other hand, P_{th} defined as the pump power when the mean photon number reaches unity and is expressed by:

$$P_{th} = A (\xi (1 - \beta) + 1 + \beta) \gamma / 2\beta \quad (5)$$

In the fit, additionally $\tau_{sp} = 1$ ns and $n_0 = 2900$ are chosen, as previously reported for QD micropillar lasers^[62] to avoid the degeneracy of the fitting parameters.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

buried-stressor method, microlasers, nanolasers, photonic microcavities, scalable quantum light sources, site-controlled quantum dots, vertical-cavity surface-emitting lasers

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